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Linking East and West African farming systems experience
into a BELT of sustainable intensification

Fonio VCA

Sustainable fonio value chain development in Ghana

Policy Brief n. 2

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SUMMARY

Fonio has gained attention in recent years as a nutritious and sustainable crop that could help address food security and nutritional challenges in West Africa and beyond. It offers an alternative to more common cereals like sorghum, millet, wheat, rice, and maize and can grow on marginal lands. Despite the great benefits associated with the crop, it is under-exploited and is considered to be an underutilized crop species in Africa. A study by the EWA-BELT project funded by EU horizon 2020 has analysed the fonio value chain in Ghana in order to identify what opportunities and barriers exist for more widespread uptake. The key issues include the following:

- Lack of modern farming equipment makes fonio cultivation and preparation for market very time-consuming
- Inadequate farming and market information deters potential growers
- There is an insufficiently developed value chain and route to market for the product
- Birds consuming the fonio during growth are a major limiting factor of fonio production.
- Harvesting, dehusking, and processing of fonio is very labour intensive
- Poor product quality has been observed in the fonio value chain
- All nodes of the fonio value chain are profitable

The introduction of cost-effective, labour-saving mechanisation at the production and processing stages of the value chain, along with access to the credit facility, improved seed, and enhanced knowledge on good agronomic practices, could significantly boost the value chain in Ghana. Marketing and promotion campaigns should be conducted to create awareness of the potential of the fonio value chain. Collective marketing and contract production could solve some of the marketing challenges of the fonio value chain. Capacity building amongst farmers and improved processing is needed. Increased funding for fonio research is recommended to develop new and improved varieties.

BACKGROUND

Fonio (*Digitaria exilis*) is the oldest west African indigenous crop and the fastest maturing cereal in the world. It is often called a miracle grain because of its ability to contribute to food security in difficult conditions. Although some studies indicate that fonio cultivation started in 5000 BC, it is an overlooked African crop and is little known to many African regions (Addai et al., 2022). However, fonio plays a vital role as a food crop for poor and vulnerable people in Africa, especially during periods of food shortages and high market prices (Borlaug, 1996). It is considered to be a priority crop for west Africa (Mbosso et al., 2020). Despite its advantages,, the cultivation and trade of fonio remain low, and it is considered to be a minor crop with no economic potential in Ghana. A key need for increasing fonio production is greater knowledge of the challenges and opportunities in Ghana's fonio value chain. This research aims to identify what constraints and opportunities exist within the fonio value chain and to identify how the value chain might be improved in Ghana.

APPROACH

Value chain analysis is used to identify and analyse key activities within the value chain and to determine how greater market value and competitiveness can be obtained. Porter (1985) initially developed the concept. Since then, a number of approaches in value chain research have been proposed (M4P, 2008; Dabat, 2018; Usman, 2016; Rashid, 2019). These sources were used to guide the approach used here and consisted in four main stages (see Figure 1).

Figure 1: EWA-BELT Value chain analyses framework

The study was carried out across the six districts of the three regions of Ghana (Northern Region, Upper East Region, and Northeast Region). A total number of 430 value chain actors were sampled (producers, aggregators, traders and processors). The total revenue, total cost, marketing cost, gross margin, marketing margin, return on investment (ROI) and benefit cost ratio (BCR) were calculated for each of the actors in the value chain to determine whether the chain was financially viable.

FINDINGS

► PRODUCTION, GENDER PREFERENCES AND MARKETING OF FONIO

Maize was the most important crop in the study area with 41% of farmers growing it, followed by groundnuts (27%), cowpea (20%), and Fonio (12%). Fonio was not considered an important crop. The study identified two types of fonio called Ipuiman and Okabuja. The Ipuiman fonio variety was preferentially cultivated by both males and females, with more males growing in than females. Okabuja was also grown by both males and females, although females preferred Okabuja to Ipuiman, possibly because of its physical appearance (see Figure 2).

Figure 2: Gender and fonio variety preference, (Source: Field survey, 2021)

► OPPORTUNITIES AND CONSTRAINTS IDENTIFIED ACROSS THE ENTIRE VALUE CHAIN

Several limitations prevented the development of the fonio value chains in Ghana. A SWOT analysis was conducted with the actors in the value chain to identify the strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats for each actor. All the actors mentioned that the good market price for fonio was a strength. However, processors in the fonio value chain noted that fonio processing was very labour intensive. Threshing and de-husking were considered to be major challenge as no equipment was available for this. Using traditional methods was very labour intensive and considered to compromise the quality of the fonio therefore reducing its market value (see Figure 3).

Figure 3: SWOT analyses of fonio value chain

► IDENTIFIED AND PRIORITIZED VALUE CHAIN UPGRADING OPPORTUNITIES

Opportunities for improving the value chain were identified and ranked by the value chain actors. These included mechanization for fonio production and processing as the most important upgrading priorities. Other suggestions included the development of bird-tolerant varieties and techniques and tools for chasing birds from fonio fields (see Table 1).

Table 1: Ranking of VC upgrading opportunities (Source: Field survey, 2021)

VC Node	Main upgrading Opportunities (VC gaps/problems)	Rank in order of importance	Solution/ introduction of new technology
Production & Processing	Mechanization –threshing, winnowing machines	1	Collaboration with organizations that can assist in mechanizing threshing and winnowing
Production	Introduction of new bird tolerant varieties, bird scaring techniques	2	Create awareness on available varieties, innovation on bird scaring techniques
Production & Processing	Improved fonio production and processing techniques	3	Capacity building
Traders & Aggregators	Establish structured markets	4	Capacity building, introduction of collective marketing and contract production
Processing	Fonio value addition and processing	5	Capacity building
Production	Use of organic fertilizer	6	Capacity building

➤ ESTIMATED MARKET VALUES ALONG THE VALUE CHAIN

All the economic performance indicators showed that fonio production was profitable. The net margins of all the actors were positive (Figure 4), and the benefit-cost ratios were greater than one implying profitability. The return on investment ranged from 11–69%. The marketing margin was greatest for producers. The share of profit per tonne of fonio also showed that producers had the greatest share (47%) followed by aggregators (22%), processors (20%) and traders (10%). Although the marketing margin for aggregators, traders, and processors is relatively low per tonne of fonio, they do have the opportunity to increase transaction volumes to compensate for the low market margin, which is not an option that is easily available to producers.

Figure 4: Per ton financial analyses of fonio value chain actors

➤ GENDER PREFERENCE OF FONIO TRAITS

Nutritional quality and the multi-utility nature of fonio were the most valued qualities for both men and women. Physical appearance was ranked 2nd by women, whilst the convenience of its storage ranked 3rd amongst men. Among all users, the ease of fonio storage was the 3rd ranked trait. Men valued fonio more for its capacity to attract high selling prices than women. Ease of seed preservation was ranked 3rd by women but 6th by men. It is clear that there are gender differences when it comes to trait preferences for fonio.

➤ FONIO MARKETING

Almost 63% of fonio farmers indicated they usually have market surpluses that they sell, whilst 37% stated they did not. The majority of fonio farmers (63%) cultivated fonio for their own consumption. The selling price of fonio was considered to be established by the producers themselves (91%) and 63% of these farmers were satisfied with the selling price of the fonio. The majority of farmers (65%) thought they were meeting market demand and 76% thought they were producing the preferred varieties.

CONSTRAINTS TO FONIO PRODUCTION ◀◀

The study showed that the majority of fonio farmers have not adopted typical agronomic practices for their fonio production. These for example include: soil bunding, drilling, use of improved varieties, fertiliser application, threshing, mixed cropping, and application of plants extracts as insecticides.

➤ VALUE CHAIN MAP WITH INFORMATION FLOW, RETURN ON INVESTMENT AND PRODUCTION DISTRIBUTION

The overview of the fonio value chain, the structure and flow of goods and services, and the linkages between various actors functioning within the fonio value chain are shown in Figure 5. This also shows the returns on investment and how they are distributed.

Figure 5: Existing fonio value chain map in Ghana

BOOSTING THE VALUE CHAIN

The potential of fonio as a viable commercial crop in Ghana is not fully realised, despite its use. This is especially true given its central role in traditional festivals. Farmers tend to use the crop within the household. To strengthen the fonio value chain, key stakeholders need to be identified and encouraged to participate in its development. These include NGOs, local agriculture officers, financial institutions, government, and business associations. These stakeholders should work together to develop interventions that can build on the opportunities and reduce the constraints within the value chain. Potential actions are shown in Figure 6.

Figure 6: Key stakeholders and their actions to boost the present fonio value chain

DISCUSSIONS

➤ **ABSENCE OF MECHANIZATION**

Lack of mechanisation is a significant barrier to commercial fonio production. Producers, traders, and processors lack adequate post-harvest technology and this is limiting fonio production. Other studies have also indicated that the lack of farm machinery to harvest, thresh, and process the fonio are significant challenges for farmers and prevents them from considering it to be a commercially viable crop (Addai et al., 2022). Threshing is done manually by beating the straw, which is laborious for women and often results in poor-quality grain (Adoukonou–Sagbadja et al., 2006). Additionally, Amanor (2019) has argued that increases in urbanisation have contributed to a scarcity of farm labour, thus resulting in rising costs for labour. This could provide opportunities for the development of labour-saving farm technologies.

➤ **LOW USE OF STANDARD AGRONOMIC TECHNIQUES FOR FONIO PRODUCTION**

Yield benefits could potentially be obtained by adopting certain practices and technologies that are not currently used for fonio. These include techniques for chasing birds out of fields, planting in rows, fonio legume rotation, access to market information, utilization of improved seeds. For example, in the study area, only two local fonio varieties were being used by farmers (Ipuiman and Okabuja). However, neighbouring Mali has introduced multiple improved varieties of fonio for their farmers to use (Sida et al., 2018). In Ghana, farmers mostly use saved seeds for production.

➤ **LACK OF CAPITAL**

Lack of credit is a major challenge identified by fonio aggregators and processors as they need financial support to improve existing or purchase new mills. This could go a long way to helping them improve the quality of fonio, for example by eliminating stones in the final product. The poor quality of the product is often perceived to result from inadequate funds for appropriate technologies in the value chain (Mbosso et al., 2020).

➤ **LACK OF LOW FONIO PRODUCT DIVERSITY**

There are few processed products derived from fonio when compared to other crops as it is often cultivated solely for household consumption rather than as a marketable product. There is a lack of knowledge regarding the growing international export market for fonio. There is also a need to identify and introduce broader options for the use of fonio. Such initiatives, particularly from processing companies, could create greater demand from urban consumers, allowing farmers to scale up fonio production, to increase profit for all actors in the value chain. Hollinger and Staatz (2015) have indicated that urban populations currently prefer access to more processed food products. In this study, producers and processors both mentioned the need to establish a structured market that would help maintain information flow among the actors to increase the production of fonio.

➤ **LACK OF MARKET AND MARKETING SERVICES**

Farmers and aggregators found inconsistent demand and fluctuations in the price of fonio in the market challenging. Retailers noted that there were spikes in demand for fonio for brief periods of the year because of its ceremonial significance to rural and urban consumers. But, overall, consumers appeared to have a positive view of fonio, as it is valued as a low input crop and a possible means of diversifying incomes for the very poor (Mbosso et al., 2020). It is important that production be influenced by market demand and that farmers have access to markets and market information to give them greater confidence in taking farm decisions.

➤ **MARKET VALUES ALONG THE VALUE CHAIN**

The study showed that fonio producers determined their selling prices and that they were also satisfied with the profit margin they earned from sales of fonio in their local market. The other actors also indicated that they could earn profits from fonio trading. However, the volume of transactions was low and an increase in traded volumes would be needed to increase profit.

➤ **GENDER PREFERENCES IN FONIO PRODUCTION**

In Ghana, women contribute significantly to the agricultural economy through their work in cultivating cash crops, even though men typically control the product and the benefits earned from it. Women are typically responsible for weeding and transplanting, both labour-intensive tasks, yet they are often invisible actors in the value chain (Amanor, 2019; Mariotti, 2021; Mbosso et al., 2020). In rural areas of Ghana, such as the Saboba District where this study took place, women often have difficulty accessing resources such as land, credit, and labour for farming. These circumstances make it particularly difficult for women farmers to improve their circumstances (Tsikata et al., 2011). In this study, only 17% of women grew fonio, and they preferred the Okabuja variety over the Ipuiman variety (see gender preference). Women's involvement in fonio farming and processing would have social and economic benefits as they often contribute more to household income (Handschuch & Wollni, 2016).

CONCLUSIONS & POLICY RECOMMENDATIONS

The constraints identified in the fonio value chain include lack of modern farming technology, inadequate farming and market information, and low interaction among the value chain actors, which limits greater economic benefit being generated. Lack of knowledge of international market demand, poor product quality, and limited access to credit are barriers to fonio value chain development. Despite these limitations, fonio is vital for local livelihoods and well-suited to the region in which it is grown currently because of its resilience to local climatic conditions. Its ability to mature rapidly improves food security for rural families during the lean season, an important role that has been extensively documented for fonio.

In order to create a sustainable commercially viable fonio value chain, we make the following policy suggestions:

- Introduce cost effective, labour friendly mechanization services at the production and processing nodes of the value chain where they are most required.
- Create marketing and promotion campaigns to increase consumer awareness of and demand for fonio.
- Capacity building at all nodes should be carried out and access to end market information should be facilitated. Demand is high during festivals and events but not year-round.
- Agricultural extension programmes to enhance knowledge, increase awareness, and access to new agricultural technologies should be facilitated.
- Access to credit will enable farmers to acquire quality inputs (seeds), and also adopt new farming technologies to address production constraints.
- New fonio recipes should be developed.
- Availability of certified seeds and development of new fonio varieties are crucial to fonio value chain development.
- Increase funding for fonio research, particularly for variety development, as this is important to the development of the fonio value chain.

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